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Electric Truck Economic Feasibility Analysis

R.Vijayagopal¹, A.Rousseau

¹*Argonne National Laboratory, 9700 S.Cass Ave, Lemont, IL, USA, ram@anl.gov*

Summary

This study quantifies the economic impact of electric trucks on a \$/mile basis for fleet operators compared to diesel powered trucks. Different vehicle classes and component sizes will be considered to determine which application and design is most likely to achieve ownership cost parity with diesel trucks. In addition, sensitivities related to cost of battery, fuel & electricity affecting the economic viability of electric trucks will be assessed. Class 4 delivery trucks will be considered as an example to demonstrate how design choices and use cases affect electric truck purchase price and efficiency. We will demonstrate that, while a short pay back period is possible for electric trucks, a full utilization of the battery energy is critical.

1 Abstract

The technical feasibility of electrified powertrains has already been demonstrated through several simulation and prototyping efforts. The economic feasibility of advanced powertrains for trucks has not yet been fully analyzed as it depends on a very large number of parameters. There are several examples of battery or fuel cell powered trucks used by fleets, but most of these vehicles are either part of technical demonstrations or incentivized by government agencies. Wider acceptance of trucks with advanced electrified powertrains will be possible when they achieve performance and economic parity with conventional vehicles. This paper examines the sensitivity of total ownership cost (TCO) for medium and heavy duty electric trucks, with respect to battery and fuel costs. The results will help identify cost targets for battery packs for various types of trucks, and will also highlight use cases where we are likely to see early adoption of these technologies.

2 Introduction

Several studies and reports predict that medium duty and heavy duty market will be ready for electric vehicles in the near future [1 - 3]. Löfstrand et al, assigned future fuel prices to establish a time frame for electric truck adoption in the European market. North American Council for Freight Efficiency has stated that electric trucks are a viable choice for 'return to base' urban operations where range is predictable and economic overnight charging is possible.[4,5]. Instead of using prototype or early electric vehicles (EVs) in the markets, this study examines simulated models of electric trucks with similar performance and cargo capacity to conventional trucks. The work quantifies the monetary impact for the vehicle owners due to changes in fuel and energy prices. This paper will also examine the importance of reducing battery cost for achieving the parity in TCO. US DOE expects to bring down battery pack cost to \$125/kWh within a few years and reduce it to less than \$100/kWh in the long term [6]. This work will help us understand how lower battery cost, combined with fuel and energy prices will shape the commercially viable roll out of electric trucks in the US market.

Commercial trucks are primarily classified according to their weight class. The vocation for which trucks are redesigned serves as a secondary classification. The truck usage determines its requirements in terms of

cargo mass , driving speed, range, electrical and mechanical accessories etc. The vehicle technical specifications in turn determines the powertrain component size requirements. In this study, we study 5 trucks across multiple classes and applications. To ensure a fair comparison between two powertrains , a set of common performance criteria is established for each type of truck as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Vehicles and required performance capabilities for each use case

Class	Purpose	Cargo (kg)	0-30 mph (s)	0- 60 mph (s)	Grade Speed 6% (mph)	Cruise Speed (mph)	Range (miles)
4	Delivery	2755	9	30	50	70	150
6	Delivery	5146	14	50	37	70	150
8	Sleeper	17329	18	60	32	65	500
8	DayCab	17324	18	66	31	65	250
8	Vocational	6874	18	76	30	60	200

Both diesel trucks and electric trucks powertrain components are sized to match or exceed the acceleration and speed requirements. The range specified in the above table is the minimum distance the trucks are expected to drive before stopping for refuelling or recharging the battery packs. It was estimated from various real world surveys, such as VIUS [7] & FleetDNA [8] as well as feedback from industry. The default tank sizes on diesel trucks allow those trucks to easily exceed this distance. Electric trucks are designed with battery packs to match the range requirement.

This study uses Autonomie [9] to model and simulate the different vehicle designs considered. Autonomie already includes vehicle models for all these trucks and provides the component and control libraries for modelling conventional and electric variants. The powertrain sizing logic used to size the powertrain components is described in prior work [10]. To simplify the cost and weight estimates, it is assumed that parts of the vehicle not directly related to the powertrain, such as chassis, body, wheels etc will remain unchanged between the conventional and electric trucks. The component sizes for each trucks are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Component size summary for comparable conventional and electric vehicles

Class	Purpose	Diesel	Electric	
		Engine (kW)	Motor (kW)	Battery Pack (kWh)
4	Delivery	165	175	220
6	Delivery	165	215	325
8	Sleeper	330	630	1575
8	DayCab	307	480	835
8	Vocational	215	300	590

For all five vehicles, the engine size of the conventional vehicle is comparable to that found in production vehicles. Medium duty trucks often span multiple weight classes and share the same engine. This paper explores the cost of owning these trucks and examines the necessary price points for diesel, electricity and energy storage systems for electric trucks to be economically attractive.

3 Vehicle Purchase Price

3.1 Main Component Costs

The manufacturing cost assumptions used in this study are described in the following section. We assume that the batteries and electric machines used for light duty applications will have to be redesigned to withstand the more demanding duty cycles expected in trucks. Current batteries manufacturing cost is estimated at \$270/kWh, if they are produced in sufficient volume. However for trucks, the production volume is expected to be low at least in the initial years, and this could result in a higher \$/kWh value for those packs. This study considers battery cost ranging from \$350/kWh to \$80/kWh to examine the sensitivity. The baseline cost values for various components are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Main component manufacturing cost comparison

Class	Purpose	Diesel		Electric	
		Engine (\$)	Gearbox (\$)	Motor (\$)	Battery Pack (\$)
4	Delivery	13400	4700	5300	53200
6	Delivery	13100	4700	6400	79300
8	Sleeper	29200	11400	18400	382200
8	DayCab	26400	10700	14300	202700
8	Vocational	17000	5800	8700	143300

3.2 Vehicle Purchase Price Estimation

Vehicle cost is estimated by adding up the manufacturing cost of the components, and applying a retail price equivalent factor. For truck application, this factor is assumed to be 1.2. In this analysis, we do not assume any grants or incentives for electric trucks. The estimated purchase price of trucks considered in this study is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Estimated purchase price of conventional and electric trucks

Class	Purpose	Purchase price (\$)	
		Diesel	Electric
4	Delivery	59100	95900
6	Delivery	73400	138000
8	Sleeper	143500	496800
8	DayCab	122300	296200
8	Vocational	96800	221800

It should be noted that these values are provided as an example for the difference in vehicle costs. As we change the component cost assumptions in the sensitivity analysis, these values will change.

4 Vehicle Energy Consumption

Fuel costs play an important part in the overall truck operational cost. For class 8 sleeper trucks, the fuel cost could even outweigh the truck purchase price. The vehicle energy consumption is measured on 3 separate drive cycles, as prescribed by U.S. EPA in their proposed regulatory framework for medium and heavy duty vehicles [11]. Two of these cycles represent highway driving and the third cycle represents the transient driving

observed in urban conditions. Based on the purpose for which each truck is used, the results from the three drive cycles are weighted differently. The weighing method put forth by U.S. EPA considers the share of vehicle operation within each cycles. For example, the Class8 Sleeper trucks runs mostly on highways. So for that type of truck, higher weight is given to the two cycles representing highway operations and only 5% weightage is given to the transient operations. The weighted fuel consumption for each truck used to examine its economic viability is summarized Table 5. The electrical consumption values are converted to diesel equivalent fuel economy for easy comparison.

Table 5. Diesel equivalent fuel economy

Class	Purpose	Weighted fuel economy mpgde	
		Diesel	Electric
4	Delivery	12.4	52.3
6	Delivery	10.1	33.4
8	Sleeper	6.7	11.5
8	DayCab	6.4	11.5
8	Vocational	7	17.3

4.1 Fuel cost

Since predicting future fuel cost is difficult, BEVs economic viability is examined for a range of diesel and electricity prices. Diesel cost varies from \$2.5/gallon to \$4/gallon while electricity cost varies from 10c/kWh to 30c/kWh. When combined with the different battery prices, we can determine under which conditions BEVs will become economically attractive.

5 TCO Analysis

This section quantifies the difference between a diesel and an electric truck ownership costs.. Some TCO factors, such as driver wages, registrations costs, tolls etc are assumed to be identical across vehicle designs. The two main factors are

1. Initial purchase price
2. Fuel/Energy cost spread over the service period of the truck.

5.1 Annual vehicle miles travelled (VMT) assumption

We assume the vehicles are used for 20 days a month, for the designed daily driving distance for the entire service period. This gives us VMT estimates shown in Table 1. It is assumed that battery replacement will not be needed during the service period of the vehicle. Later sections of the paper will examine the impact of VMT on TCO parity

5.2 Vehicle service period assumption

The service period changes for different types of trucks. The vehicle lifetime is expected to be 15 years for all trucks except Class8 Sleeper. Typical sleeper trucks are used for long haul for less than 5 years. After the initial 5 years, they get used in regional or short haul operations. We assume the sleeper trucks to have a residual value of 45% of purchase price when the fleets dispose them at the end of 5 years. If trucks are used for their full lifetime of 15 years, there is no residual value expected at the end of their service period. The variation of residual values as a function of the service time is shown in Figure 1

Figure 1. Variation of assumed residual value of a truck as a percentage of purchase price w.r.t. years of service

With the assumptions shown in Table 6, Autonomie estimates that the sum of purchase price and fuel costs over the service period for a class8 sleeper as \$0.62/mile. This is similar to the estimate made by American Transportation Research Institute (ATRI) as well.[12]

Table 6. Assumptions for TCO calculation

Class	Purpose	VMT	Service period (years)	Discount rate (%)	Battery Cost	Electricity cost	Diesel cost
4	Delivery	18000	15	7	\$350/kWh to \$80/kWh	10c.kWh to 30c/kWh	\$2.5/gallon to \$4/gallon
6	Delivery	18000					
8	Sleeper	120000	5				
8	DayCab	30000	15				
8	Vocational	24000					

The actual cost of battery packs, diesel, and electricity charges could vary for every fleet. The range considered here, would help account for such variations.

6 Results

This section summarizes the TCO parity comparison for all trucks. Sensitivity related to battery and energy cost, along with daily trip distance and associated electric range will be considered. Based on Figures 2-4, it can be inferred that among the vehicles considered, the most promising candidate to achieve purchase price parity with diesel trucks is the Light HD (Classes 2 to 4) electric delivery trucks. Medium HD (Classes 5-6) and larger trucks face a tougher challenge due to the need for larger battery packs.

Figure 2. Purchase price parity comparison of all vehicles considered in this study

Figure 2 shows the difference in purchase price between diesel and electric trucks. Values under zero shows that EVs are more expensive than diesel trucks.. Light HD trucks could see purchase price parity when battery pack cost drops to \$80/kWh.Light HD trucks can achieve TCO parity with diesels even with costlier battery packs, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Difference in TCO in using an electric truck over a diesel truck for parcel delivery operations in urban centres. The profit or loss associated with operating an electric delivery truck is quantified in terms of \$/mile in this figure. The green region indicate conditions where the electric truck is profitable. With present diesel prices at \$3/gallon, class4 (Light HD) delivery trucks could see TCO parity if the battery pack cost is at \$225/kWh. Figure 4 shows a similar analysis for class 8 trucks designed as Vocational, DayCab and Sleeper. The heavier electric trucks in this analysis will be cost effective only if battery pack cost drops under \$100/kWh or if diesel prices rise to \$4/gallon or higher..

Figure 4. Difference in TCO in using heavy duty electric truck for various vocations

This shows that for today's diesel price and cost of batteries, early adopters of these vehicles might incur a loss varying from 5c/mile to 30c/mile based on the type of truck they operate, if they do not receive any grants or tax incentives to offset the cost of acquiring these trucks.

6.1 Impact of driving range and daily trip distance on TCO

The above figures show purchase price parity will be difficult to achieve for most trucks even if the battery pack cost reaches the lower limits considered in this study. This means that fuel savings is critical to achieve TCO parity. Fuel savings is directly linked to the distance driven by the trucks. This brings the focus to the assumptions electric truck will be driven for the full designed driving range during its service period.

If daily trip distance is shorter than the designed electric range, it means that the expensive battery pack in EVs are not being fully utilized. Price of diesel trucks are largely unaffected by such variations in daily trip distance. If daily trip distance is lower than the designed range of the EV, it reduces the potential for fuel savings and makes an EV less economically attractive. For this analysis, we will focus on class 4 delivery vans and the class 8 daycab trucks. We will examine how the TCO parity is affected if VMT is reduced.

FleetDNA data shows that designed range of 150 miles is sufficient to cover most of the delivery truck use cases, but a majority of those routes are under 75 miles. Similar trends are found for other types of trucks too.

Figure 5. Distribution of daily trip distance for delivery trucks from FleetDNA

6.1.1 Case 1: Designed for 150 miles but used for shorter daily driving

We consider two additional cases to examine the sensitivity to VMT, where the daily trip distance is set to 45 miles and 75 miles respectively to evaluate a 50th percentile and 90th percentile case from FleetDNA. This changes the annual vehicle miles used for the TCO estimate to 4800miles and 9000miles respectively. If we assume a diesel cost of \$3/gallon, TCO parity can be observed for light HD delivery van only if battery pack costs less than \$125/kWh and \$150/kWh respectively. This is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. TCO parity check for class4 delivery truck with reduced VMT

The shaded regions represent the lines represent the conditions where the electric truck has a lower TCO over the diesel counterpart.

6.1.2 Case 2: Designed and used for shorter daily driving

This case assumes a scenario where the battery is sized to specifically meet the daily driving requirements. As we see from FleetDNA data, about half of the daily trips are under 45 miles. If we have three use cases where daily driving distances are 150, 75 and 45 miles respectively, we can get vans that are designed with smaller battery packs, just for those distances. Under such a situation, the electric truck will be economically attractive even under the present day cost of battery packs and diesel. This is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. TCO parity check for class4 delivery truck with reduced VMT and resized battery pack

If a delivery truck is designed for 75 mile range and driven 75 miles every day, it would have TCO parity with a diesel truck even if the battery cost is \$300/kWh, if the recharging of battery could be done at 10-12 cents per kWh.

6.2 Impact of shorter service period

This study assumes a service period of 15 years for medium duty trucks. While it is true that many fleets own the vocational trucks for the entire lifetime of the trucks, the fleets would want to see a shorter payback time for their additional investment on electric trucks. This payback period could be as low as 3 years. Class 4 delivery truck designed and driven for a daily trip of 75miles is used for this analysis. Figure 8 shows the purchase price estimates and the difference between the diesel and electric truck prices. If battery cost drops below \$170/kWh, then electric truck is cheaper to purchase.

Figure 8. Estimated purchase price of diesel and electric trucks designed for 75 mile range

We estimate an energy consumption of 770Wh/mile for the delivery truck. The operating cost associated with this is roughly 8c/mile if price of electricity is assumed as 10c/kWh. For a diesel truck, the fuel cost will be 24c/mile to operate at \$3/gallon. For every mile, the EV will save 16c for the operator. At 18000 miles a year, savings for the operator is \$2900 per year. The present value of such savings over the future years is quantified as shown in Figure 9

Figure 9. Present value of fuel savings over the service period of the vehicle

If the value of fuel savings exceed the purchase price difference we see in Figure 8, then the investment on electric vehicle is a good investment. If the payback period is set at 5 years, then it would be justifiable to pay about \$12000 more for the electric truck.

For various service durations, the TCO parity with diesels is achieved in the shaded region. A vehicle that will be used for 15 years can save close to \$26000 in fuel cost over the service period, and it will be viable even if battery costs \$300/kWh but if the electric truck should achieve TCO parity in 3 years, the battery cost will have to drop to \$275/kWh.

Figure 10. impact of service duration on TCO parity of a class4 electric truck

7 Conclusions

This study shows that ‘Light HD’ trucks are the most promising among the vehicles considered in this study to achieve TCO parity with diesels. Class 8 long haul operations is the most challenging use case for electric trucks to achieve economic parity with diesels.

Economic disadvantages in having a generic design that can meet a 99 percentile use case is illustrated in this work. An under utilized battery is a major hurdle in achieving TCO parity. For class4 delivery trucks it was found that TCO parity could be achieved, even with current battery prices, if the vehicle is designed and used for short routes. Such a design may not meet the needs of all fleets, but there could be real world users who can successfully adopt electric trucks, even if the payback period is relatively short. This also points to the need for modular battery sizes based on specific needs

This study highlights the need to additional research by considering real world use cases and explore how additional powertrains compare to conventional vehicles in the near future. Variations in daily driving distance may be unavoidable for many use cases. Fast charging EVs or PHEVs could be explored as the solution to address range uncertainties.

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10 Presenter Biography

Ram Vijayagopal is the technical manager for Vehicle Technology Assessment at Argonne National Laboratory. He is responsible for quantifying the energy saving potential of technologies using modelling and simulation. After working at Mahindra & Mahindra and Hitachi Automotive Systems, he joined Argonne in 2008. He received his bachelor's degree in engineering from University of Kerala and a master's degree in engineering from University of Michigan. He has authored over 20 papers in the area of advanced vehicle technologies.

Aymeric Rousseau is the Manager of the Vehicle Modelling and Simulation Section at Argonne National Laboratory. He received his engineering diploma at the Industrial System Engineering School in La Rochelle, France, in 1997. After working for PSA Peugeot Citroen in the Hybrid Electric Vehicle Research Department, he joined Argonne National Laboratory in 1999, where he is now responsible for the development of Autonomie. He received an R&D 100 Award in 2004 and Vehicle Technologies Program Award in 2010. He has authored more than 40 technical papers in the area of advanced vehicle technologies.